

Multi-RAT Fiber-Wireless Technologies towards 6G networks

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ABSTRACT

At the dawning of the beyond 5G era, broadband last mile connectivity is stimulating rapid developments in optical and wireless technologies that will efficiently handle the traffic generated by mobile users and demanding network applications. To this end, multiple Radio Access (multi-RAT) technologies operating at various millimeter wave (mmWave) frequency bands, e.g., V-/E-/D-band are being actively pursued, in parallel with the investigation of efficient fiber wireless fronthaul schemes, e.g. Analog Radio over Fiber (aRoF) or Intermediate Frequency over Fiber (IFoF), to deliver low-complexity, broadband, last-mile connectivity. However, integration of such novel technologies in an actual mobile network infrastructure remains a challenge, as it needs to support compatibility with the network operators' equipment. The current talk aims to present a holistic Fiber Wireless (FiWi) connectivity, demonstrating the co-existence of Analog and Digital RoF traffic along with flexible, reconfigurable point-to-multipoint connectivity to multi-RAT antenna units. Experimental results on high capacity FiWi fronthaul links operating in the V- (60 GHz) and D- (145 GHz) will be presented. Moreover, end-to-end, integrated real-time traffic and network operation will also be discussed and experimentally presented, indicating a possible technology roadmap towards multi-RAT 6G networks.

Keywords: 5G/6G communications, Radio Access Networks, mmWave. Fronthaul.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the dawning of the 5G/6G era, mobile networks are forecasted to unravel a whole new set of emerging bandwidth-demanding services, such as Enhance Mobile Broadband (eMBB) communications, Fixed Wireless Access (FWA) services, Augmented and/or Virtual Reality (AR/VR). Delivering such services through the mobile networks will inevitably lead to a drastic surge in the Fiber Wireless (FiWi) traffic capacity circulated through the network [1]. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) require a 20 Gb/s peak traffic transported to the antenna for 5G networks [1-3], while some recently defined 6G KPIs already predict nearly abundant bandwidth to a cell-site with 1 Tb/s hauling capabilities. Boosting the wireless capacities is one side of the story, as on the other hand such excessive data rates are certainly bound to stress the capabilities of the optical transport network. To this end, there seems to be a broad consensus that efficient optical fronthaul schemes, e.g. Analog Radio over Fiber (aRoF) or Intermediate Frequency over Fiber (IFoF) [4], can achieve spectrally efficient transmission scheme, while multiple Radio Access (multi-RAT) technologies typically operating at various millimeter wave (mmWave) frequencies between 30 - 300 GHz, to realize low-complexity, broadband, last-mile connectivity

In this talk, we present our vision of a flexible and reconfigurable network capable of integrating multiple radio terminals, operating at different mmWave frequency bands, allowing to efficiently allocate different radio resources to different cell sites [5]. Specifically, we present the envisioned FiWi architecture comprising of an $N \times N$ AWGR as an all passive any-to-any optical interconnect based on its wavelength routing functionality and subsequently, we discuss the excessive losses introduced by the use of mmWave frequencies for four different bands proposed towards 6G networks to provide some indicative insight on its impact on the cell radii. For this purpose, we experimentally present two FiWi mmWave links, including a D-band FiWi link with 6 GHz 3dB bandwidth and up to 128-QAM transmission at 900 Mbaud at a fixed direction with fixed angle [6], as well as a V-band FiWi link with 0.95 GHz 3dB bandwidth and up to 32-QAM at 100 Mbaud with RF beamsteering within a 90° degree sector [7], aiming to present an experimental comparison between the two FiWi links. Finally, we also discuss the integration of the proposed FiWi links with a real-time services delivered end-to-end through appropriate BBU fronthaul interface with Software Defined Network (SDN) controlled capabilities for proper wavelength assignment capabilities. In a nutshell, the current talk aims to present a holistic view of the development of optical and wireless technologies for supporting multi-RAT environments in 6G networks.

2. NETWORK ARCHITECTURE AND MMWAVE-LOSSES

Targeting to handle the large wealth of emerging network applications and services with widely varying requirements, the envisioned FiWi network architecture towards 6G networks aims to integrate various mmWave frequency bands in a centralized and reconfigurable FiWi network architecture that can selectively activate a different RRU and frequency band at several different cell sites in a programmable fashion. The proposed architecture is visually illustrated in Fig. 1(i), comprising of an $N \times N$ AWGR acting as an any-to-any

Figure 1. i) Illustration of the Fiber Wireless (FiWi) multi-Radio Access Technologies (multi-RAT) supporting multiple millimeter-wave bands and reconfigurable inter-connectivity through an $N \times N$ AWGR, ii) free space path loss for four frequency bands for 6G network, including 3.5GHz (5G NR), 28GHz (n257), 60GHz (n263) and 145 GHz (D-band), assuming 1W of transmitted power and annotated radii for -100 dBm received power.

switching node. The Centralized Unit (CU) hosts a pool of BBU fronthaul interfaces, equipped with tunable wavelength laser emission properties or a multi-wavelength WDM optical Tx/Rx array, e.g. for generating a 4λ -WDM optical fronthaul transmission. The generated tunable wavelength transmission is then optically connected to the input ports of the AWGR which routes the traffic of each input port to a different output port based only on its wavelength, hence allowing to reconfigure the topology and BBU-to-RRU interconnectivity. At the antenna site, various radio frequencies are being considered and standardized for the beyond-5G/6G era. Namely, the proposed frequency bands include the 3.5GHz known as 5G NR, the 28GHz standardized as n257, the 60GHz referred as n263 and the 145 GHz in the D-band. For these frequencies, the losses versus the distance from the RRH have been numerically estimated based only on the free space path loss modelling (Friis transmission equation/formula), assuming a 1W of power radiated at the Tx output, as depicted in Fig. 1(ii). As it can be seen, by arbitrarily (and without loss of generality) considering a minimum accepted rf power level of -100 dBm, the obtained allowable distance was measured to be 683m, 85m, 40m and 16m respectively for the 3.5 GHz, 28 GHz, 60GHz and 145 GHz frequencies, indicating the tremendous decrease of the cell radii when increasing the frequency and implying a significant densification of the Radio Access Network (RAN), necessitating multiple, densely populated RRUs to be reconfigurably connected and selectively activated.

3. DEVICES AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The current section presents the experimental setup used for the demonstration and comparative evaluation of the two developed FiWi mmWave fronthaul links, including either a novel broadband D-band antenna pair featuring a highly directional beam at a fixed (0° degree) angle and low phase noise or a V-band phased array antenna with RF beamsteering capabilities. In order to evaluate the performance of D-band FiWi X-haul link, an experimental transmission setup has been established in the uplink communication path as depicted in the layout of Fig.2(i)-upper inset, while a photo of the D-band Tx antenna is shown in Fig.2(ii). The D-band Tx antenna was placed at a distance of 50 cm apart from the Rx antenna. Both the Tx and Rx units featured a flat frontend panel of 256 radiating elements, co-packaged with an integrated MMIC RF up-conversion stage. The Tx input ports were inter-connected to the four output ports of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) that synthesized an IF between 1 – 10 GHz with the data being imprinted on the I, Q differential signals. Towards generating the D-band carrier, RF up-conversion of the IF signal was utilized, that performed mixing between the IF signal and the Local Oscillator (LO) output that was ranging between 11-14 GHz generated by an external signal generator and multiplied by $\times 12$ using the internal integrated MMIC mixing stage. The RF up-conversion stage allows producing a stable amplitude and low-phase noise, overcoming the use of complex heterodyne mixing schemes or the beating of two laser sources that typically produce high phase noise. At the Rx side, the received signal was amplified by a 25dB-gain D-band amplifier before feeding the signal to a symmetrical RF down-conversion stage, converting it back to the IF signal. The D-band radiating front-panel exhibited dimensions of $40 \text{ mm} \times 40 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm}$, hosting a specially designed slot array of 16×16 , termed as Electrical Bandgap architecture of an all passive beamforming unit and depicted in Fig. 2(ii), achieving 30 dBi gain in a highly directional beam. Owing to this design by Sinowave, the developed antenna with its flat profile can easily fit on building-walls, roof-tops or lampposts with easy mounting-placements. More details on the antenna elements has been reported in [6]. More specifically, after the D-band transmission, the IF signal was optically transmitted using low-cost 10GHz optics based on a simple and efficient scheme of Intensity Modulation/Direct Detection (IM/DD) on an IF over Fiber (IFoF). The IF signal was amplified electrically by commercial driver amplifiers (SHF) at up to 5V, before being connected to an MZM LiNbO_3 modulator, thus imprinting the IFoF signal on a 1550nm

Figure 2.i) Experimental setup used for selectively evaluating the D- and V-band FiWi IFoF transmission links and photos of the ii) D-band transmitter antenna unit and iii) the V-band phased array antenna

subcarrier of Tunable Laser Source (TLS). The optical IFoF was then transmitted across a standard 1km-long Single Mode Fiber (SMF) spool, reaching 10 GHz PIN photoreceiver for o-e.

Equivalently, the FiWi uplink experimental transmission setup for the V-band links is shown at the lower-inset of Fig. 2(ii). In this case, the D-band link is replaced by a V-band Rx phased array antenna (PAA) and a portable V-band Tx antenna Transmitter. The PAA integrates a 32-element radiating tile that was emulating a mmWave RRH unit in an uplink transmission scenario. The 60GHz wireless signal was received by the PAA and then downconverted to a 5 GHz IFoF, so as to be optically transmitted across the 1 km spool of SMF. The Tx antenna was configured to operate in the 57-64 GHz spectral band featuring a horn antenna unit of 22-dBi gain and a packaged I/Q modulator, with an integrated RF up-conversion stage. The Tx horn assembly was fed with the I and Q components of the radio signal generated by the AWG and power by an LO around 10 GHz, that was multiplied by 6x-times at mixing stage. After 1m V-band wireless transmission over the air, the signal was received by the PAA Rx tile that hosts 32 radiating elements, each with a dipole of 120° isotropic radiation and 6 dBi gain, placed at the tile front-panel. The PAA tile was integrated on low temperature ceramics while the RF signal chain with the V-band to RF down-conversion stage, Low Noise Amplification (LNA) stage and phase shifting element (ϕ) was integrated on a Tile Feed PCB. The complete V-band PAA assembly is shown in Fig. 2(iii). The 32 IF channel outputs were then combined together to produce the 5GHz IF output that carries the wirelessly transmitted data, before being modulated on the optical transmission setup with the 10 GHz LiNbO₃ MZM modulator and photodiode. Housing 32 channels that can be selectively configured and tuned, the current PAA allows operating it either in an isotropic reception of a complete sector, when activating only one of the 32 elements/signal-chain channels, or in an RF beamsteering operation with a directional beam supporting at least 9 different angles of reception as has been thoroughly characterized and demonstrated in [1].

4. Experimental Results

Both the FiWi mmWave links were experimentally characterized statically with single tone and dynamically using data transmission signals, as shown in Fig. 3.

Initially, the D-band FiWi link was characterized with the results depicted in the upper row of Fig. 3. The FiWi link was statically characterized in terms of bandwidth by feeding the horn Tx with a single IF tone at 1 GHz and an LO that was continuously swept. After sweeping the LO oscillator, the wirelessly transmitted tone could sweep the D-band carrier frequency from 145 GHz up to 165 GHz, while evaluating the received output power after the Rx antenna, so as to evaluate the available spectrum. As shown in the measurements in Fig. 3(i), the wireless link exhibits a 3dB bandwidth of around 6GHz and a 10 dB bandwidth of 11.2 GHz. Moreover, the performance of the FiWi link in single-band data-transmission was experimentally evaluated using 0.9 Gbaud waveforms at 1GHz IF produced by the AWG. Single carrier waveforms were utilized, including QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM and an 128-QAM of increasing spectral efficiency. A PRBS9 was employed and an aggregate of 2000 symbols, based on the maximum supported number of symbols and the respective spectrum supported by the combined operation of the AWG and signal analyser at the time of experimentation. Fig. 3(ii) depicts the RF spectrum of the 16-QAM FiWi signal, occupying an 1.17 GHz spectrum and exhibiting an average SNR of 32 dB. The constellation diagrams and the respective achieved EVM values of the received signals as evaluated by the signal analyser are depicted in Fig. 3(iii) for the four waveforms. As it can be seen, all four waveforms were distinctly demodulated with clear separation of all 2000 symbols. The respective EVM values recorded were 5.6%, 3.3%, 3.9% and 2.7% for the QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM and 128-QAM waveforms, all meeting the respective threshold requirements established by 3GPP for radio and RoF transmissions, resulting to a maximum data rate of 6.3 Gb/s for a single IF-band and a spectral efficiency of 5.38 b/s/Hz for the FiWi channel.

Subsequently, the characterization of the FiWi V-band channel through the PAA is presented. In this case the PAA was configured to operate in an RF-beamsteering operation, directed at 0° degree angle of reception.

Figure 3. Experimental results for the D-band FiWi link, including i) characterization of the spectral bandwidth versus the carrier frequency (red and green marker for the 3dB and 10 dB bandwidth) , ii) RF spectrum of an 900 Mbaud signal with 32 dB SNR, and iii) constellation diagrams and achieved EVM values for waveforms of QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM and 128-QAM of 900 MBd, and experimental results for the V-band FiWi link: iv) bandwidth versus carrier frequency, v) RF spectrum of an 300 MBd signal with 26 dB SNR, and vi) constellation diagrams with EVM values for QPSK at 300 MBd, 16-QAM at 250 MBd and 32-QAM of 100 MBd.

Similar results have been obtained for different angles of transmission [1]. In order to test the supported bandwidth and carrier frequencies, a similar single tone sweep experimental test was implemented and transmitted by the horn Tx. The received signal and its RF power were monitored by the signal analyser, while the IFoF tone was tuned from 3.25 GHz up to 6 GHz, which corresponds to carrier frequency from 58.75 to 61.5 GHz, as shown in Fig. 3(iv). The obtained curve revealed a central peak-gain at 4.6 GHz with a 500 MHz nearly-flat pass-band (i.e. around 60.1 GHz), while the 3 dB and 10 dB bandwidths were measured to be 0.95 GHz and 2.7 GHz respectively. The FiWi V-band links was also evaluated in data transmission scenarios including variable modulation formats starting from 300 Mbd QPSK and scaling up to 250 Mbd 16-QAM and 100 Mbd 32-QAM. The obtained RF spectrum for the case of the 300 Mbd QPSK is depicted in Fig. 3(v), extending across a 400 MHz-wide spectral bandwidth, while achieving an SNR value of 26 dB, being lower than the 32 dB for the case of the D-band mainly due to more challenging RF chain of the PAA configuration, including 32-parallel channel with separate LNAs and phase shifting terms. However, the constellation diagrams and the respective EVM values achieved for each of the 300 Mbd QPSK, 250 Mbd 16-QAM and 100 Mbd 32-QAM signals are represented in Fig. 3(vi), exhibiting EVM values of 17.1 %, 10.2 % and 7.9 % that all satisfy the 3GPP requirements for the EVM thresholds, and thus achieving data rates of 0.6 Gb/s, 1 Gb/s and 0.5 Gb/s per beam respectively capable of being steered anywhere within a 90° degree sector, i.e. from -45° up to +45° angle of incidence. The maximum obtained spectral efficiency was of 3.7 b/s/Hz for the case of the 32-QAM signal.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A holistic view of Fiber Wireless technologies supporting reconfigurable optical interconnectivity and multi-RAT environments is presented, shaping a path towards efficient, broadband and low-power 6G networks.

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